

Reflection and Exploration on the Cultivation of Talent Majoring in Automation in Local Universities in the AI Era

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Abstract:

This paper delves into the challenges encountered in the cultivation of talent majoring in automation in the context of the AI era, and proposes a series of practical strategies for local universities. These strategies encompass the establishment of a curriculum system with AI features, the implementation of personalized mentorship guidance models, the design of innovative mechanisms for student incentive and evaluation, and the enhancement of professional development for teaching teams. The research findings of this paper not only provide valuable guidance for the teaching reform of automation majors in local universities but also serve as a reference for other institutions in similar fields of major construction.

Keywords: cultivation of talent; automation ; Artificial Intelligence; teaching reform.

1. Introduction :

Currently, artificial intelligence (AI) technology has made significant breakthroughs in model construction, algorithm optimization, and hardware development, becoming the core driving force in the global race for technological dominance. Its importance has risen to the level of national strategic competition. The groundbreaking advancements in AI have not only brought tremendous progress to the technology itself but have also permeated various industries and had a profound impact on numerous sectors of society. The era of global AI has already arrived.

The development of automation, closely associated with AI, is evidently facing new challenges. Automation disciplines must keep pace with the trends by incorporating AI-related knowledge into their curriculum considerations. This ensures that students understand the basic principles, algorithms, and applications of AI, enabling them to apply AI technology to solve practical problems. Moreover, it fosters students' innovative thinking and expands their opportunities for development in fields such as intelligent manufacturing, intelligent control systems, and automation equipment and tools.

Simultaneously, given that the impact of AI extends far beyond the field of automation, understanding AI can also help students in automation disciplines stay abreast of the latest developments in other disciplinary areas. This enhances their ability to integrate technologies and provides a foundation for interdisciplinary project communication and

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collaboration. Consequently, it better prepares them to meet the evolving needs of future society.

2. Current State of Domestic and International Research

At the 2013 Hannover Industrial Fair[1][2], Germany introduced the "Industry 4.0" strategy aimed at spearheading an industrial revolution and maintaining manufacturing leadership. The core of this strategy is intelligence, which covers four main themes: intelligent production, factories, logistics, and services, closely related to AI. In 2015, the Chinese government released "Made in China 2025" upon this, essentially China's version of "Industry 4.0," emphasizing the acceleration of the deep integration of new generation information technologies with manufacturing, advancing the depth of intelligent manufacturing, and achieving the strategic goal of becoming a manufacturing powerhouse.

To address this challenge, universities around the world are prioritizing the cultivation of top-notch, innovative engineering and technical talent. They are actively exploring new educational concepts and forming the development strategies of the so-called "New Engineering Disciplines." For example, in 2017, MIT launched the "New Engineering Education Transformation" (NEET) program, which emphasizes interdisciplinary and project-based learning methods. AI is incorporated into the curricula of multiple engineering disciplines. Students not only learn traditional engineering knowledge but also gain exposure to the fundamentals and practical applications of AI. Technical University of Munich (TUM) has undertaken a series of educational and research initiatives in the fields of New Engineering Disciplines and AI. They offer interdisciplinary programs such as Robotics and Cognition and Intelligence Master's programs to equip students with specialized knowledge and skills in robotics technology and artificial intelligence, meeting the demands of future technological advancements. Cornell University in the United States provides interdisciplinary courses like "Artificial Intelligence, Robots, and the Design of Future Education" and advocates close collaboration between the College of Engineering and the university's AI laboratories.

China, under the active promotion of the Ministry of Education, is committed to the development of New Engineering Disciplines. It has successfully implemented numerous innovative engineering education reform projects. In these projects, research related to automation considers AI as an integral part, combining it with traditional automation disciplines to form a new model of training called "Artificial Intelligence + Automation," also known as intelligent automation. Significant efforts have been made in core curriculum systems, faculty team construction, and the integration of research and practical experience, aiming to cultivate versatile talents capable of adapting to future technological changes and industrial demands. Some universities have directly established schools of Artificial Intelligence and Automation on the basis of their original automation departments, integrating research and teaching resources in the field of AI to improve resource utilization efficiency, promote interdisciplinary collaboration, and thus drive the integration of AI and

automation disciplines.

The above indicates the proactive adjustments and efforts made by universities in their educational philosophies and approaches to adapt to the development of AI.

3. Challenges Faced by the Introduction of AI into the Talent Training System of Automation

Despite achieving certain effectiveness in integrating AI into automation education, Chinese domestic universities also face significant challenges: the rapid development of AI and the evolving demands of industries. Local universities encounter difficulties in talent training for "Artificial Intelligence + Automation," struggling to introduce specialized teachers due to financial constraints, and facing numerous obstacles in achieving training objectives. Additionally, compared to traditional majors in automation and other engineering disciplines, AI possesses a series of unique developmental characteristics. These characteristics reflect the inherent complexity and interdisciplinary nature of AI as a field, posing significant challenges to talent training in the automation profession.

(1) Fast Technological Iteration

Technological innovation in the field of AI is advancing at an unprecedented pace, with new algorithms, models, and technologies emerging constantly, continually pushing the boundaries of industry development. Breakthroughs in fields such as machine learning and deep learning, along with significant improvements in computing power, have collectively propelled the rapid development of AI technology. In this context, designing and updating curriculum systems to remain synchronized with technological developments has become extremely challenging.

(2) complex knowledge system

The research and application of AI in the field involve deep-level content from multiple disciplines, resulting in a vast knowledge system. For example, computer science provides the foundation for algorithms and programming languages. Statistics becomes the cornerstone for building complex models and data analysis. Cognitive science and neuroscience provide essential references for mimicking brain functions. Additionally, the development of AI also encompasses knowledge from fields such as philosophy, psychology, linguistics, and more.

(3) extensive research direction

The research scope of the AI field is extremely broad, covering multiple branches such as machine learning, computer vision, natural language processing, and robotics. These research areas span from fundamental theoretical exploration to the innovation of applied technologies, offering students diverse career development paths. However, this also leads to students' confusion when selecting their personal development directions.

(4) Ethical and legal issues.

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With the widespread application of AI technology, ethical and legal issues have become increasingly prominent. Ensuring fair and unbiased decision-making in AI systems, protecting personal privacy, and preventing misuse all require individuals trained in this field to possess not only technical capabilities but also moral and legal awareness. It is essential for them to develop their own values and ethics within the context of AI, so as to address issues related to fairness, privacy, and responsible use of AI systems.

4. Main Ideas for Training Automation Talent in the Era of AI

Based on the aforementioned characteristics of AI development and the challenges it poses to the training of professionals in automation, we have several ideas for the construction of talent training models.

4.1 Curriculum Development with AI Emphasis

In response to the influence of AI, numerous Chinese universities have significantly adjusted the core curriculum framework for automation majors, incorporating courses such as machine learning, deep learning, and computer vision to provide students with a systematic understanding of professional knowledge[3][4].

However, as mentioned earlier, technological innovation in the AI field is progressing at an unprecedented pace, making it exceedingly difficult to maintain synchrony between curriculum frameworks and AI advancements, especially for undergraduate institutions with relatively limited faculty resources. Therefore, with a focus on stability and continuity, our primary measures involve reinforcing and improving the teaching content related to AI within the existing curriculum framework, emphasizing the understanding and mastery of fundamental theories and methodologies in the AI domain.

(1) General Education Courses

Within our general education curriculum, courses closely related to AI include "Introduction to Artificial Intelligence" (second semester of the first year), "Engineering Ethics" (second semester of the second year), and "Advanced Mathematics" (first and second semesters of the first year).

For instance, "Introduction to Artificial Intelligence" is tailored for students across all majors, with a specific emphasis for automation majors on understanding the development history of AI and intelligent control. This includes highlighting the transition from theory to practice and the interrelation between AI and intelligent control, along with key technologies and applications at various stages. This helps students grasp the evolution and future directions of these two related fields while emphasizing the role and importance of foundational disciplines such as advanced mathematics, linear algebra, mathematical statistics, and computer science in AI and automation.

"Engineering Ethics" not only covers the fundamental concepts, principles, and theories of ethics but also focuses on addressing ethical issues specific to automation and artificial intelligence technologies. Topics include the potential employment issues and social

inequalities arising from automation technology replacing traditional job positions, as well as discussions on robot ethics, including moral responsibility, autonomy, and human-robot relationships, illustrated through examples such as the ethical dilemmas of autonomous driving cars and privacy controversies of facial recognition technology.

"Advanced Mathematics" underwent partial revisions to strengthen content related to multivariable calculus and vector algebra and analytic geometry. Multivariable calculus forms the basis for parameter optimization in neural networks, while vector operations and spatial geometric descriptions in analytic geometry provide foundations for computer vision.

(2) Discipline Foundation Courses

Adjustments were made to the syllabi of "Linear Algebra" and "Probability Theory and Mathematical Statistics," two fundamental courses crucial in the AI domain. Many core concepts and techniques in AI rely on relevant mathematical knowledge. Given the critical role of eigenvalues and eigenvectors in dimensionality reduction techniques such as PCA (Principal Component Analysis) and SVD (Singular Value Decomposition), additional class hours were allocated to the eigen decomposition section. Linear transformation knowledge is applicable in image filtering, transformations, and other operations, hence an increase in class hours for this section. "Probability Theory and Mathematical Statistics" was reinforced with additional class hours on maximum likelihood estimation and Bayes' theorem, widely applied in model training and parameter optimization within artificial intelligence. Strengthening these knowledge areas provides essential mathematical foundations for students in data modeling, model training, and inference in the field of artificial intelligence.

(3) Major-Specific Courses

In our specialized courses, two courses relevant to artificial intelligence are "Intelligent Control" and "Computer Vision." In "Intelligent Control," emphasis was placed on increasing class hours dedicated to fuzzy control, which is relatively simple to learn and implement and finds wide application in dealing with uncertain objects and decision-making. While the class hours for neural networks remained unchanged, a stronger emphasis was placed on understanding basic concepts and differentiating them from deep learning. Other aspects of intelligent control, such as genetic algorithms, primarily focus on conceptual understanding to minimize students' academic burden. "Computer Vision" intensified class hours on image feature extraction, convolutional neural networks (CNNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), and other areas to equip students with fundamental theoretical foundations required for tasks like image classification and object detection.

(4) Elective Courses

The development of elective courses is relatively flexible and diverse, allowing students to cross disciplines. Options include courses such as "Data Structures and Algorithms," "Machine Learning," "Data Mining and Big Data Analysis," and "Python Programming." "Data Structures and Algorithms" form the foundation of AI algorithms. "Machine Learning" is one of the core technologies of AI. "Data Mining and Big Data Analysis" enable students to

master techniques such as data preprocessing, feature extraction, and pattern discovery, supporting AI model training and application. Python is one of the commonly used programming languages in the AI field. These elective courses provide opportunities for students with spare capacity and a particular interest in AI to delve deeper into the subject.

4.2 Personalized Mentorship Guidance Model

As previously mentioned, the rapid advancement of AI technology has made it difficult for students to fully grasp all the knowledge in this field. In such a scenario, students must choose research directions based on their personal interests and professional focus. Therefore, mentorship guidance becomes particularly crucial and valuable at this critical juncture[5][6].

(1) Fine Management to Enhance Bidirectional Selection Effect

Currently, a tradition has formed in our automation discipline where graduate mentors guide undergraduate students. We have implemented measures for bidirectional selection, requiring faculty members to teach at least one theoretical course and lead one lab session for automation major students before the bidirectional selection process. The theoretical course imparts professional knowledge and also allows observation and identification of students' diverse traits and potential during the teaching process. Meanwhile, lab sessions typically involve designing open-ended questions or small-scale projects to provide students with opportunities to exercise creativity and teamwork. Through these processes, mentors can essentially gauge a student's dedication to research and resilience, while students gain deeper insights into the teaching styles and research directions of various mentors, enabling them to make more informed choices for their future academic pursuits.

(2) Personalized Guidance to Enhance Student Engagement

Undergraduate students at local universities usually engage in research with mentors for three main purposes: enhancing employability, increasing acceptance rates for postgraduate studies, and pursuing pure interest. For students aiming to enhance employability[7], we require research groups to provide certain technical skills training, such as guiding students in mastering popular programming languages and machine learning libraries, encouraging involvement in practical projects related to automation and artificial intelligence, and facilitating collaborative training with mentors from external enterprises to guide students in applying AI technology to solve specific industrial or societal problems. For students aiming for postgraduate studies, research groups typically offer opportunities for them to be responsible for a module or an entire project, thereby enhancing their research experience. Additionally, mentors guide students in writing papers and publishing them in relevant journals to improve their research paper writing skills and academic influence. Currently, some undergraduate students have published articles in core journals, and some have even published papers included in the SCI database. For students driven purely by interest, they are allowed to explore freely in areas combining automation with artificial intelligence, and regular sharing sessions on the latest developments and trends in

AI and automation fields are held to stimulate students' curiosity and creativity.

(3) Hierarchical Training to Optimize Efficiency of Teacher-Student Interaction

In local undergraduate universities, the student-to-faculty ratio is relatively high, meaning that teachers need to attend to a larger number of students, resulting in naturally limited individual guidance time for each student. However, for undergraduate students who are at the early stages of their academic journey, investing a certain amount of time in guidance is essential for their research initiation and skill enhancement. To address this challenge, our institution has adopted an innovative "hierarchical research guidance model." In this model, mentors primarily guide graduate students, while graduate students serve as mentors to undergraduate students. By establishing this mentor-graduate-undergraduate research hierarchy, it ensures that mentors can efficiently pass on research experience and knowledge while maintaining control over the overall direction of the projects.

The implementation of this model helps to bridge the guidance gap caused by inadequate faculty resources and also provides graduate students with opportunities to enhance their teaching and communication skills. It is a win-win strategy that maximizes the unleashing of undergraduate students' research potential within limited faculty resources, propelling them to take solid steps on the path of research.

4.3 Student Incentives and Assessment Methods

In order to foster undergraduate students' enthusiasm for integrating AI into their research activities, we have carefully adjusted the incentive and assessment system for students majoring in automation.

(1) Optimization of Laboratory Resource Allocation

The college stipulates that students joining mentor research groups have priority access to the "university's undergraduate innovation laboratory", which is affiliated with our "National Experimental Teaching Demonstration Center for Electrical Engineering and Electronics." This laboratory possesses abundant teaching and experimental resources. Various subject competitions participated in or hosted by the college are organized by the innovation laboratory. Therefore, only students who are members of the laboratory are eligible to participate in these competition projects.

(2) Improvement of Grading, Awards, and Credit Recognition Mechanisms

In subject competitions, if the topics chosen by students majoring in automation are related to the field of artificial intelligence, such as intelligent vehicle competitions, robot challenges, etc., the awards received will enjoy additional scoring advantages. When evaluating the distribution of scholarships, the selection of "Excellent Student Awards," and the recognition of "Outstanding Graduates" and other honorary titles, research achievements serve as important evaluation criteria.

(3) Optimization of Graduation Project Topic Selection

During the topic solicitation stage of graduation projects, guiding teachers are required to ensure that a certain proportion of topics are related to artificial intelligence and

automation technology. In order to further encourage students to incorporate artificial intelligence into their projects, the grading criteria for defense presentations include a specific scoring item focusing on the integration level of artificial intelligence. Current trends indicate an increasing number of students choosing topics that combine artificial intelligence and automation technology for their graduation projects, often achieving excellent results.

4.4 Faculty Development

Synthesizing the aforementioned analyses, it is evident that while updating curriculum content and employing motivational strategies are important in cultivating students, they serve merely as ancillary measures. The crux lies in the guidance and influence of undergraduate mentors, whose professional qualities and abilities are paramount in nurturing automation students with an AI background.

Confronted with the challenge of relatively insufficient local faculty resources and the recruitment of new instructors, we have implemented the following measures to strengthen the mentor team: ① Primarily relying on the cultivation of the existing faculty team, supplemented by an active recruitment strategy for new instructors. Emphasis is placed on attracting teaching and research personnel with an AI academic background, encouraging and supporting instructors to regularly participate in AI training and academic exchange activities. ② Implementing a multi-faceted collaborative education model, facilitating the establishment of a cross-disciplinary Artificial Intelligence College, enhancing collaboration between different departments, academia, and industry, as well as deepening the integration of industry, academia, and research[8]. These measures leverage external resources to compensate for deficiencies in the knowledge of our faculty. ③ Encouraging and supporting instructors to closely integrate research with practical applications, actively participate in research projects, and translate research findings into new productive forces and tangible economic benefits, thereby creating a positive feedback loop to further stimulate enthusiasm for research among faculty and students.

In recent years, the majority of doctoral talents recruited by the Department of Automation possess a background in AI. The school has also established the Artificial Intelligence College under our auspices, organizing regular training and academic exchange activities. These measures have significantly promoted interaction between departments, expanded the application scenarios of automation combined with AI technology, and increased practical opportunities for both faculty and students.

5. Conclusion

With the rapid development of AI and its significant impact on various aspects of society, particularly in the realm of talent cultivation at universities, exploring the development of the automation discipline under the influence of AI has become an unavoidable topic.

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The solutions proposed in this paper focus on strengthening the education of foundational knowledge related to artificial intelligence within the existing curriculum framework, laying a solid theoretical foundation for students. This paper particularly emphasizes the importance of a personalized mentorship system. In this model, mentors are not only providers of knowledge but also guides for students' academic journeys. Through refined management, personalized guidance, and hierarchical training, mentors can tailor learning plans and research directions to each student's specific situation, thereby maximizing their potential. The methods proposed in this paper may provide some useful references for local undergraduate institutions in integrating AI technology into the automation discipline.

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